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Research Article

AWARENESS OF PHYSICIANS ABOUT THE ROLE OF INTERVENTIONAL RADIOLOGISTS IN PATIENT CARE- A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract:

Objective To map out the current provision of interventional radiologists in patient care

Design Cross-sectional study. We designed a descriptive cross-sectional study using questionnaire that included a total of 16 items. The questionnaire was pre-tested and validated in a pilot sample. The intra-rater and inter-rater reliability was also checked and it was found to be 0.912 and 0.871, respectively. **Results** Our cross-sectional study was done among medical residents practicing in the western province of Saudi Arabia, which included three main cities (Figure 1). We had about 46.70% (n=99) residents from R1, 23.11% (n=49) from R2, 13.68% (n=29) from R3, and 10.85% (n=23) from R4 programs, with only 5.66% (n=12) from R5, respectively.

Conclusion The findings of our study show that there is a lack of awareness among medical residents regarding IR and its application in the clinical practice. The perceived awareness among the participants could be mainly due to insufficient exposure to this sub-specialty in the undergraduate medical curriculum. Hence, it is suggested that the curriculum of undergraduate should be updated by incorporating IR at both basic and clinical levels of the medicine program in Saudi Arabia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Interventional radiology (IR) is a new minimally invasive medical field that utilizes imaging techniques to undergo minimally invasive procedures in patients. Interventional radiology performs precise procedures by using needles, catheters, and wires to reach the targeted site under image guidance such as fluoroscopy, ultrasound, CT, and MRI. Many procedures start by passing a needle through the skin, which is also called pinhole surgery. (1) IR includes various procedures that are rapidly expanding, which commonly include treatment for peripheral arterial diseases, aneurysms, varicose veins, tumors, renal stones, etc. Interventional radiology procedures are also considered a better alternative for open surgeries because they have fewer risks, lower cost, quicker recovery times, and shorter hospital stay. (2, 3)

Despite the wide spread application of IR procedures in clinical practice, there is still a huge gap in teaching the same for medical graduate students. (4) Data from different countries shows that there are no specific or structured curricula in teaching modules and medical students receive very little exposure during their study in this specialty. (5-7) This deficiency might lead to little participation of medical residents in IR procedures in the clinical practices. So, it has become an essential field that the awareness among medical students and residents has become a vital process.

In Saudi Arabia, the data related to the use of IR procedures related to its applications, awareness, and its coverage in the medical curricula are limited in the literature. However, an increasing numbers of interventional radiologist and hospitals that provide IR services are obvious. (8) Studies conducted in other countries shows that the knowledge among medical students related to IR was poor compared to other specialties. (9-11) A study conducted in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia in 2013 also reported that the knowledge among medical students is poor. (8) Hence this study is aimed to explore the understanding and knowledge of interventional radiology among medical residents working in general surgery, internal medicine, obstetric and gynecology, and pediatric departments in the western region hospitals of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

We designed a descriptive cross-sectional study using questionnaire that included a total of 16 items. The questionnaire was pre-tested and

validated in a pilot sample. The intra-rater and inter-rater reliability was also checked and it was found to be 0.912 and 0.871, respectively. The questionnaire was divided into two parts, Part I included Sociodemographic details and part II had questions related to the knowledge about interventional radiology training, procedures, clinical responsibilities, and previous experience of residents with interventional radiologist.

The participants were briefed about the need, importance, and benefits of the study after ensuring the confidentiality of the information they provide. We included medical residents working only four specialties such as general surgery, internal medicine, obstetric and gynecology, and pediatric departments of hospitals in Jeddah, Makkah, and Taif region only (Western region of Saudi Arabia). We included all those who gave consent for participation without any gender discrimination after assessing the inclusion criteria. The questionnaire was converted to an online survey format type and was sent to 310 medical residents after getting the contact information according to the inclusion criteria and we received a total of 212 completed responses thus giving us a response rate of 68.38.

The data obtained were transferred and entered in a Microsoft Excel Sheet, and then was subjected to statistical analyses. Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 23 (SPSS, IBM Corp., USA) was used for statistical analyses. Descriptive statistics were used in the form frequencies and percentages for presentation of data. A significance value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Our cross-sectional study was done among medical residents practicing in the western province of Saudi Arabia, which included three main cities (Figure 1). We had about 46.70% ($n=99$) residents from R1, 23.11% ($n=49$) from R2, 13.68% ($n=29$) from R3, and 10.85% ($n=23$) from R4 programs, with only 5.66% ($n=12$) from R5, respectively. (Figure 2)

When the participants were enquired about the knowledge about the specialty, only 5.19% ($n=11$) agreed that they have 'excellent' knowledge about IR and its applications in clinical practice. Also, 25% agreed that their knowledge is 'good' about this specialty. Additionally, 51.89% agreed that they have 'adequate' knowledge regarding IR. However, 17.92% ($n=38$) reported that their knowledge is 'poor'. (Figure 3)

Figure 1: Region of residence (hospitals)

Figure 2: Distribution of participants according to years of residency

Figure 3: Knowledge about the IR among the participants

When the participants were asked about some procedures whether they are part of IR or not, the responses showed that their knowledge and awareness among these IR procedures are not satisfactory. The details of this awareness regarding the IR procedures are depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Participants awareness about different types of IR procedures

Types of IR procedures	Agreed		Disagreed	
	%	n	%	n
Image guided biopsy or drainage	81.60%	173	18.40%	39
Uterine artery embolization	71.23%	151	28.77%	61
Coronary angioplasty or stenting	63.68%	135	36.32%	77
Vascular angioplasty	58.96%	125	41.04%	87
Radiofrequency ablation of tumor	57.55%	122	42.45%	90
Peripheral vascular bypass	35.38%	75	64.62%	137
Gastrostomy tube	28.77%	61	71.23%	151
Bone marrow biopsy	24.53%	52	75.47%	160
Biliary drainage	45.75%	97	54.25%	115
Central venous access	41.04%	87	58.96%	125
Inferior vena cava filter	59.43%	126	40.57%	86
Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt	56.13%	119	43.87%	93

When participants were asked whether an Interventional Radiologist has got a hospital admitting responsibility for patients who require any procedures, 53.30% (n=113) agreed for this question. Of the 212 medical residents, 46 (21.27%) believe that an Interventional Radiologist has a separate outpatient department for consultation. It was also reported by 34.43% (n=73) of residents that they referred patients directly to an interventional radiologist.

A 33.49% of the participants reported that they would benefit ‘very much’ in their clinical practice if they were provided with additional education in IR in the curriculum. Only 9.43% (n=20) reported that they will ‘not at all’ benefit from such additional education regarding the IR. (Figure 4)

Figure 4: participants opinion on benefits from additional education in IR

In our analysis, we found that 93.40% of participants agreed that ‘attending a presentation about interventional radiology topics at conferences’ is one of the methods that acquire additional knowledge in IR and 52.36% mentioned ‘problem based small group learning and discussion’ as other methods. About 44.34% mentioned that all the four options can be used to acquire additional education in IR. (Figure 5) When the patients were asked to rank the role of IR in managing patients in each hospital, 61.79% (n=131) mentioned it as ‘very important’ and only 0.47% (n=1) mentioned it as not important. (Figure 6)

The satisfaction response of participants showed that 14% (n=29) were ‘very satisfied’ of the IR services in their work (hospital) setting. Approximately 10% (n=21) were ‘very dissatisfied’ with it, and 36% (n=77) had a neutral response regarding the IR services in their hospital setting. (Figure 7)

DISCUSSION:

IR is a well-established discipline and occupies a key role in treating many medical and surgical conditions instead of the more traditional invasive procedures that often involve the risks of general anesthesia and open surgery. (12) Our study was an attempt to explore the current awareness and perceptions about IR among medical residents in the western region of Saudi Arabia. The findings of the study showed that there is a reasonable awareness of IR in the super-specialty among the study participants. Majority of the residents had adequate knowledge about IR as a sub-specialty and its applications in clinical practice. A study done by de Gregorio in Spain among medical students showed that second year and fourth year showed an adequate and poor level of awareness, respectively. Majority of the students strongly agreed that IR should be included in medical schools' curriculum. (13) It should be considering that IR has gained formal recognition as a sub-specialty in its way and need to be given predominant consideration in the medical curriculum.

The findings of the study show that 71.23% knew that Uterine Artery Embolization (UAE) is a procedure performed by an interventional radiologist. Uterine fibroids (leiomyomas) are the most common benign neoplasm of the female pelvis shows a high prevalence. UAE is a procedure that has shown a high success rate in managing these leiomyomas through infarction of these fibroids by occluding their vascular supply. (14) This procedure commonly uses single arterial access, and rarely bilateral access is also being tried

in some cases usually without regional or general anesthesia. (15)

It was surprising to note that about 41.04% of the participants in our study were not aware that vascular angioplasty is an IR procedure. Vascular angioplasty (VA) is a non-surgical procedure with or without stenting that is used to open narrowed or clogged arteries that involve applying an inflatable balloon-tipped catheter through the skin in extremities. (16) Similarly, residents showed a lack of awareness in other IR procedures such as Radiofrequency ablation of tumor (IRA), Peripheral vascular bypass, Inferior vena cava filter, Bone marrow biopsy (IR- guided), etc. The reason for the less awareness among residents about these procedures could be due to limited exposure to this sub-specialty or could also be due to lack of teaching from the specialists themselves. Another study that was conducted in Canada found that about 30% of students reported that they didn't have any exposure to IR procedures in their curriculum. (10) These findings collectively show that students have less exposure to this sub-specialty in the medical schools and there is a need to show improvements in this area.

The present study also reveals that residents express a desire to acquire knowledge and skills in this specialty mainly through attending presentations at IR conferences, problem-based small group learning and discussion, reading peer-reviewed articles, etc. One practical solution for the present situation is that IR faculty should conduct lectures and problem based small group discussion in the clinical years of the medical program. The

lectures should be given on IR procedures/interventions that coincide with the pathophysiology of the diseases. For example, the indications, contraindications necessary equipment, positioning, techniques, complications of Peripheral Vascular Stent Insertion should be described during the discussion of peripheral arterial occlusive lesions. This could also be achieved by inviting a radiologist for a group discussion without causing a conflict with other specialties.

The study also showed that most of the residents (62%) considered IR as an important specialty in managing patients at their hospital setting. We also noted that approximately 42% of the residents had some form of satisfaction regarding the IR services at their hospital settings. Ministry of Health and medical schools should consider the suggestions and requests for making a compulsory clinical rotation in clinical radiology or IR Department for medical graduates pursuing a degree in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. This could positively improve the knowledge and skills of graduates in IR as studies have shown that early exposure to clinical imaging or radiology would stimulate interest and also improves the approach and perception of medical students to this specialty. (17-19)

Some of the limitations of our study should be addressed before generalizing the findings. The first limitation is that as in all surveys there is a possibility of response bias, with residents more interested in IR are more likely to respond to the questions. However, the predicted awareness regarding the IR was similar to other studies. (9-11). There is also a possibility of regional bias as the knowledge of the participants and their attitudes about IR are not generalized in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of our study show that there is a lack of awareness among medical residents regarding IR and its application in the clinical practice. The perceived awareness among the participants could be mainly due to insufficient exposure to this subspecialty in the undergraduate medical curriculum. Driven by the technologic advances in the field of medicine, the applications of minimally invasive procedures have increased drastically. Hence, it is suggested that the curriculum of undergraduate should be updated by incorporating IR at both basic and clinical levels of the medicine program in Saudi Arabia.

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